

SHAPE CONTROL OF LAMINATED FRAMES UNDER UNCERTAIN THERMAL AND MECHANICAL LOADS USING PIEZOELECTRIC ACTUATORS

Sarp Adali¹, Ibrahim S. Sadek², John C. Bruch, Jr.³, James M. Sloss⁴, Izzet U. Cagdas¹

¹*School of Mechanical Engineering, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban, South Africa*

²*Department of Mathematics and Statistics, American University of Sharjah, Sharjah, UAE*

³*Dept. of Mechanical and Environmental Engr, University of California, Santa Barbara, CA, USA*

⁴*Department of Mathematics, University of California, Santa Barbara, CA, USA*

SUMMARY: Optimal piezo actuator sizes and locations for a laminated composite frame under bending and thermal load uncertainties are determined with the objective of minimizing the deflection under worst case of loading. The bending moments generated by the piezo actuators are used for deflection control. The frame is subjected to a tip load which lies in an uncertainty domain with regard to its direction as well as to a uniform temperature loading. The worst case of loading depends on the size and location of the actuators leading to a nested problem of optimization (design) and anti-optimization (uncertainty problem). The fibre content of the composite is also determined so as to minimize the weight and deflection of the frame noting that piezo actuators are more effective for structures with low stiffness. The fibre content of the material has a direct influence on the structural stiffness making this parameter an effective tool in the shape control of structures.

KEYWORDS: Optimal piezo sizes, Uncertain loading, Minimum deflection, Laminated frames

INTRODUCTION

Quite often the loads acting on a structure under operational conditions are not known *a priori* resulting in load uncertainties which in turn lead to unexpected deformations if not taken into consideration at the design stage. Designs based on deterministic loading conditions become ineffective under uncertain loads leading to unexpected failures. The present study is aimed at formulating and solving a robust piezo shape control problem for a frame structure which is controlled by piezoelectric actuators bonded to the top and bottom surfaces of the structure and subject to load uncertainties. Previous works on optimal design under uncertain loading include references [1-3] where composite laminates were studied. An extensive survey of the design under load uncertainty is given by Cherkaev and Cherkaev [4].

The particular problem involves an L-shaped frame with a tip load which is clamped at one end. The load is uncertain in the sense that it may act in any direction within a 90 degree angle during its service life and the design should produce minimum tip deflections in the vertical and horizontal directions. In addition a temperature difference between the top and bottom of the frame may exist leading to thermal deflection. Two piezo actuators are attached to each arm of

the frame and the size and location of each piezo should be determined such that the tip deflections will be the minimum possible given that the load can act in any direction. It was found that the best locations for the actuators are at the clamped end of the arms reducing the problem to an actuator size problem. The optimum size of each actuator is determined such that the tip deflections of the frame in the positive and negative vertical and horizontal directions under the given load uncertainty is minimum.

Previous studies on shape and deflection control of one-dimensional structures using piezoelectric actuators mostly involved beams [5-11]. In these studies various aspects of shape control were discussed. In Refs. 8 and 9, the deflection expressions for beams controlled by induced strain actuators were derived for various boundary conditions. Further work on the subject involved control of deflections using NITINOL [12], shape memory alloys [13] and photostrictive optical actuators [14]. The present paper extends these results to composite frames subject to load uncertainties.

BASIC EQUATIONS AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

Let the L-shaped frame ABC be clamped at point A and free at point C as shown in Figure 1. The length and moments of inertias of sections AB and BC are denoted by L_1 , L_2 and I_1 and I_2 , respectively. Two piezoelectric patch actuators of length b_1 and b_2 are symmetrically bonded at sections AB and BC with their mid-points at distances a_1 and a_2 from points A and B, respectively (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Geometry of the composite frame and the piezo patch actuators

The piezoelectric actuators are bonded symmetrically onto the top and bottom of sections AB and BC and when actuated with an out-of-phase electric field perpendicular to their surfaces, they generate moments m_1 and m_2 concentrated at the end points of the patches. Let the height of the section be h and the thickness of the piezoelectric layer h_p . The moments m_1 and m_2 are given by

$$m_1 = E_a h_s (h_s + h_1) \Lambda, \quad m_2 = E_a h_s (h_s + h_2) \Lambda \quad (1)$$

where E_a is the Young's modulus of the actuator and Λ is the induced strain [8]. These moments are to be used to minimize the tip deflection of the frame caused by the horizontal and vertical loads P_H and P_V acting at point C. These loads are uncertain in the sense that their magnitudes are not known *a priori* except a constraint is imposed on the loads such that they lie in an uncertainty domain U which should be specified. Two examples of the uncertainty domains are given as

$$U_1 = \{P_H, P_V; P_H, P_V \geq 0; P_H^2 + P_V^2 \leq P^2\} \quad (2a)$$

$$U_2 = \{P_H, P_V; P_H, P_V \geq 0; 0 \leq P_H, P_V \leq P\} \quad (2b)$$

as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Uncertain load domains

The directions of the loads are in the positive x and y directions. In the uncertainty domain U_1 , the loads lie on a circle ABC and their magnitudes can be defined by a single parameter θ which is the clockwise angle from the x axis. In this case θ becomes the uncertainty parameter. In the case of the uncertainty domain U_2 , the loads can take any values on the boundaries AD and DC of the square OADC. The dimensions and locations of the piezo patch actuators satisfy the inequalities

$$b_1/2 \leq a_1 \leq L_1 - b_1/2, \quad b_2/2 \leq a_2 \leq L_2 - b_2/2 \quad (3)$$

Let H_C and V_C denote the horizontal and vertical deflections of point C due to actuator patches and δ_H and δ_V the horizontal and vertical deflections of point C due to loads P_H and P_V and the thermal loading T . The deflections H_C and V_C can be expressed as

$$H_C = f_H(b_1, b_2, a_1, a_2, m_1, m_2), \quad V_C = f_V(b_1, b_2, a_1, a_2, m_1, m_2) \quad (4a)$$

The deflections δ_H and δ_V due to loads can be expressed as

$$\delta_H = g_H(P_H, P_V, T; v_f), \quad \delta_V = g_V(P_H, P_V, T; v_f) \quad (4b)$$

where v_f is the fibre content of the composite. The locations and the lengths of the actuator patches, i.e., a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2 are free parameters which can be used to minimize the deflections of point C under loads P_V, P_H and T . However, the actuators are most effective when they are closest to the fixed ends and away from the free end C. This observation reduces the number of design parameters to two, namely, b_1 and b_2 with the patch locations $a_1 = b_1/2$ and $a_2 = b_2/2$ expressed in terms of the lengths of the actuators.

We first formulate the deterministic design problem which serves to illustrate the differences between the design problems with and without known loads. The deterministic design problem can be stated as

$$\min_{b, v_f} |d_H(b, v_f; P)| = \min_{b, v_f} |\delta_H(b, v_f; P) + H_C(b)| \quad (5)$$

$$\min_{b, v_f} |d_V(b, v_f; P)| = \min_{b, v_f} |\delta_V(b, v_f; P) + V_C(b)| \quad (6)$$

where b and P are the design and load vectors given by

$$b = (b_1, b_2), \quad P = (P_H, P_V, T) \quad (7)$$

In Eqs. (5)-(7) P_H, P_V and T are given loads and d_H and d_V are the deflections of point C in the x and y directions due to the combined effect of the actuator patches and the given loads. In the case of the uncertain design problem, the loads P_H and P_V belong to one of the uncertainty domains given by eq. (1) and the minimum deflection problem can be stated as

$$\min_{b, v_f} \max_{P \in U_i} |d_H(b, v_f; P)| \quad (8)$$

$$\min_{b, v_f} \max_{P \in U_i} |d_V(b, v_f; P)| \quad (9)$$

where $i=1$ or 2 and U_i is given by Eq. (2). Thus, the deflections are maximized over the loads to obtain the least favourable loading and minimized over the lengths of the actuator patches leading to a nested optimization problem.

MICROMECHANICS MODEL

In order to determine the fibre volume content v_f in an optimal manner, elastic constants E_{11} , E_{22} , G_{12} and ν_{12} has to be expressed in terms of v_f as these constants appear in the deflection expressions. The expressions for the elastic constants as a function of v_f can be obtained from micromechanics models. The micromechanics model to be used in the present study involves an elementary cell of a unidirectional composite material with the axis of revolution taken along the fibre direction. The elastic behaviour of an elementary cell of the composite material can be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{13} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} n & l & l & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ l & k+m & k-m & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ l & k-m & k+m & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2m & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2p & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2p \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{11} \\ \epsilon_{22} \\ \epsilon_{33} \\ \epsilon_{23} \\ \epsilon_{13} \\ \epsilon_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where k , l , m , n , and p are the Hill's elastic moduli; n is the uniaxial tension modulus in the fibre direction (direction 1), k is the plane-strain bulk modulus normal to the fibre direction, l is the associated cross modulus, m and p are the shear moduli in planes normal and parallel to the fibre direction, respectively. A composite with a reinforcing phase volume fraction v_f , matrix Young's modulus E_m and matrix Poisson's ratio ν_m is considered. Using the Mori-Tanaka method, the Hill's elastic moduli are found to be [15]:

$$k = \frac{E_m \{E_m c_m + 2k_r(1+\nu_m)\} [1 + v_f(1-2\nu_m)]}{2(1+\nu_m) [E_m(1+v_f-2\nu_m) + 2c_m k_r(1-\nu_m-2\nu_m^2)]} \quad (11)$$

$$l = \frac{E_m \{c_m \nu_m [E_m + 2k_r(1+\nu_m)] + 2v_f l_r(1-\nu_m^2)\}}{(1+\nu_m) [2c_m k_r(1-\nu_m-2\nu_m^2) + E_m(1+v_f-2\nu_m)]} \quad (12)$$

$$n = \frac{E_m^2 c_m (1+v_f - c_m \nu_m) + 2c_m v_f (k_r n_r - l_r^2) (1+\nu_m)^2 (1-2\nu_m)}{(1+\nu_m) [2c_m k_r(1-\nu_m-2\nu_m^2) + E_m(1+v_f-2\nu_m)]} + \frac{E_m [2c_m^2 k_r(1-\nu_m) + v_f n_r(1-2\nu_m + v_f) - 4c_m l_r \nu_m]}{2c_m k_r(1-\nu_m-2\nu_m^2) + E_m(1+v_f-2\nu_m)} \quad (13)$$

$$p = \frac{E_m [E_m c_m + 2(1+v_f)p_r(1+\nu_m)]}{2(1+\nu_m) [E_m(1+v_f) + 2c_m p_r(1+\nu_m)]} \quad (14)$$

$$k = \frac{E_m [E_m c_m + 2m_r (1 + \nu_m) (3 + \nu_f - 4\nu_m)]}{2(1 + \nu_m) \{E_m [c_m + 4\nu_f (1 - \nu_m)] + 2c_m m_r (3 - \nu_m - 4\nu_m^2)\}} \quad (15)$$

where k_r , l_r , m_r , n_r and p_r are the Hill's elastic moduli for the reinforcing phase. The expressions for the moduli of the composite as functions of the stiffness constants are determined for a unidirectional composite as follows [16]:

$$E_L = n - \frac{l^2}{k}, \quad E_T = \frac{4m(kn - l^2)}{kn - l^2 + mn}, \quad G_{LT} = 2p, \quad \nu_{LT} = \frac{l}{2k} \quad (16)$$

DETERMINISTIC DESIGN PROBLEM

In the case of the deterministic problem, the minima of the deflections are given by

$$d_H(b, \nu_f; P) = 0, \quad d_V(b, \nu_f; P) = 0 \quad (17)$$

and can be realized for large enough actuator moments m_1 and m_2 . From Eqs. (9), (10) and (14), it follows that the design parameters b_1 , b_2 and ν_f can be determined as the solution of the nonlinear system of equations

$$\delta_H(b, \nu_f; P) + H_C(b) = 0 \quad (18)$$

$$\delta_V(b, \nu_f; P) + V_C(b) = 0 \quad (19)$$

The solution of Eqs. (18) and (19) giving the optimum sizes of the actuators are denoted as b_1^* and b_2^* , and the optimum fiber content as ν_f^* . For low values of the moments generated by the actuators, the actuators cover the entire length of the arms AB and BC.

DESIGN UNDER UNCERTAIN LOADS

The uncertainty domain in the present study is taken as U_1 where P_H and P_V satisfy

$$P_H^2 + P_V^2 \leq P^2, \quad P_H, P_V \geq 0 \quad (20)$$

where the loads are applied in the positive x and y directions (Fig.2). Thus

$$P_H = P \cos \theta, \quad P_V = P \sin \theta, \quad \theta \in [0, \pi/2] \quad (21)$$

since they lie in a circular domain in the first quadrant and the uncertain loads can be expressed in terms of the uncertainty parameter θ . The horizontal deflection can be minimized with respect to the design parameter b_1 and the problem can be expressed as

$$\min_{0 \leq b_1 \leq L_1} \max_{0 \leq \theta \leq \pi/2} |d_H(b_1, \nu_f; \theta)| \quad (22)$$

where maximization over θ produces the least favorable load case. The optimization/anti-optimization problem expressed by Eq. (22) can be solved by numerical optimization and the solution is denoted by b_{1u}^* . The corresponding θ maximizing the deflection (referred to as the least favourable deflection) is denoted as θ_u . The problem of minimizing the vertical deflection $d_V(b_1^*, b_2, v_f; P)$ can be expressed as

$$\min_{0 \leq b_2 \leq L_2} \max_{0 \leq \theta \leq \pi/2} \left| d_V(b_{1u}^*, b_2, v_f; \theta) \right| \quad (23)$$

where b_{1u}^* is obtained from the solution of problem (22). The solution of problem (23) is denoted as b_{2u}^* . The problems (22) and (23) are solved by a numerical optimization scheme which involves stages of maximization with respect to θ (anti-optimization) and minimization with respect to b_1 or b_2 (optimization). The overall results are investigated to establish the effect of the fibre volume content and to determine the best value of v_f .

CONCLUSIONS

Optimal sizes of piezo patch actuators which control the deflection of an L-shaped composite frame is to be determined for a tip load which is uncertain in the sense that it may act in any direction within a 90 degree angle. The tip deflection under uncertain load is required to be minimum regardless of the direction of the load leading to a robust design. In this case the direction of the load is an uncertainty parameter which is computed by maximizing the tip deflections. The uncertainty problem leads to an optimization/anti-optimization problem involving the actuator sizes and the load direction, respectively. In cases where the moments generated by the actuators are not strong enough, the deflections cannot be made zero by piezo control and the full length of the arms are used for the actuators to minimize the deflections.

In the absence of a robust design, the worst case deflection becomes substantially higher under an uncertain loading. The actuator sizes depend on the moment generated by the actuator in a monotonic way with the actuator length becoming smaller with increasing moment.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation under Award No. INT-9906092 and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration under Award No. NND04AB82C and Stirling Dynamics, Inc.

REFERENCES

1. Adali, S., Richter, A., Verijenko, V.E., "Non-probabilistic modelling and design of sandwich plates subject to uncertain loads and initial deflections", *Int J Engineering Sciences*, Vol. 33, 1995, pp.855-866.
2. Adali, S., Richter, A., Verijenko, V.E., "Minimum weight design of symmetric angle-ply laminates under multiple uncertain loads", *Struct Multidisc Optim.*, Vol. 9, 1995, pp.89-95.

3. Adali, S., Lene, F., Duvaut, G., Chiaruttini, V., "Optimization of laminated composites subject to uncertain buckling loads", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 62(3-4), 2003, pp.261-269.
4. Cherkaev, E. and Cherkaev, A., "Principal compliance and robust optimal design", *Journal of Elasticity*, Vol. 72 (1-3), 2003, pp. 71-98.
5. Main, J.A, Garcia, E., Howard, D., "Optimal placing and sizing of paired piezoactuators in beams and plates", *Smart Mater. Struct.*, Vol. 3, 1994, pp. 373-381.
6. Chandrashekhara, K. and Varadarajan, S., "Adaptive shape control of composite beams with piezoelectric actuators", *J. Intell. Mater. Syst. Struct.*, Vol. 8, 1997, pp. 112–124.
7. Abramovich, H., "Deflection control of laminated composite beams with piezoceramic layers–closed form solution", *Compos. Struct.*, Vol. 43, 1998, pp. 217–231.
8. Gaudenzi, P., Barboni, R., "Static adjustment of beam deflections by means of induced strain actuators", *Smart Mater. Struct.*, Vol. 8, 1999, pp. 278-283.
9. Ang, K.K., Reddy, J.N., Wang, C.M., "Displacement control of Timoshenko beams via induced strain actuators", *Smart Mater. Struct.*, Vol. 9, 2000, pp. 981–984.
10. Yang, S. and Ngoi, B., "Shape control of beams by piezoelectric actuators", *AIAA J.*, Vol. 38, 2000, pp. 2292–2298.
11. Aldraihem, O.J. and Khdeir, A.A., "Precise deflection analysis of beams with piezoelectric patches", *Composite Structures* , Vol. 60, Issue 2 , May 2003, pp. 135-143.
12. Baz, A., Chen, T., Ro, J., "Shape control of NITINOL-reinforced composite beams", *Composites: Part B*, Vol. 31, 2000, pp. 631-642.
13. Moallem, M., "Deflection control of a flexible beam using shape memory alloy ctuators", *Smart Mater. Struct.*, Vol. 12, 2003, pp. 1023-1027.
14. Shih, H.R., Watkin, J., Tzou, H.S., "Shape and displacement control of beams with various boundary conditions via photostrictive optical actuators", *Proceedings of IMECE'03, 2003 ASME International Mechanical Engineering Congress*, Washington, D.C., November 15-21,2003.
15. Shi D-L, Feng X-Q, Huang Y.Y, Hwang K-C, Gao H., "The Effect of nanotube waviness and agglomeration on the elastic property of carbon nanotube-reinforced composites", *Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology*, Vol. 126, 2004, pp.250-257.
16. Berthelot J-M., *Composite Materials: Mechanical Behavior and Structural Analysis*, Springer-Verlag, New York,1999.